

CULTURAL INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL WORKERS AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT, WELFARE PROGRAMS IN SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS IN RIVERS STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11519945>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Abstract

This study examined the Cultural influence of social workers and community development, welfare programs in selected Local Government Areas in Rivers State. Cultural influence was measured by cultural effectiveness, Cultural involvement, Consistency of culture, Adaptable Culture and Flexible Culture while social worker development and welfare was measured by performance, growth, job satisfaction, success and social development. The study formulated five research objectives and questions. Simple percentages, frequency tables and mean were used as data analysis techniques. From the analysis, all 400 copies of the questionnaire were properly filled out and retrieved. This represents a 100% retrieval rate. Table 4.1 indicated that there were more females than males among the respondents that participated in the study. Table 4.2 showed that most of the respondents were between the age of 30 and 39 years. Table 4.3 showed that the majority of the respondent had Bachelor Degrees or Bachelor of Science as their highest educational qualification. Analysis of the research questions proved that some of the items found that there is significant relationship between the variables such that we rejected while other found no significant relationship such that we accepted. the study conclude that this study examined cultural influence of social workers and community development, welfare programs in selected local government areas in Rivers State. We recommend that social workers in the selected Local Governments in Rivers State should adopt culture that best enhances employee performance and efforts should be directed to ensure effectiveness of culture in the local governments, local government councils should ensure that incentives are provided to staff and ensure that the culture of the area is integrated with the objectives and the operational order of the social workers, workers should be provided with all trainings and orientations to ensure that culture is consistent with social workers in the local government as this can enhance the performance and welfare of the people and culture is an essential ingredient of social worker performance and welfare, the study recommends that

the local government should and the social workers should ensure that cultures are adaptable.

Keywords: Cultural Influence, Social Workers, Community Development, Welfare Programs.

INTRODUCTION

Social workers promote peace by empowering communities and by helping them in the development of their abilities and to acquiring tools to overcome oppressive environments. Social workers help them to achieve their goals by building self-confidence and motivation, by raising awareness of their situation, and by building collective actions to promote access to rights and services. Social workers create and recreate social relationships through critical thinking and access to social policies that promote people's autonomy. Thus, individuals transform their realities by informed action and by creative ways to make distinctive alternative choices, which have increasingly demonstrated the capacity to increase the control over their lives through agency (Simionatto, 2016).

The workplace environment is dynamic and always changing to keep employees performing at their highest levels. Extreme pressure from stakeholders, the workplace environment has a detrimental effect on workers well-being, leading to employee absences, demotivation, and decreased productivity. A wonderful place to work cultivated by actions like fostering a workplace culture of respect, inclusion, diversity, and innovation. The workplace of the twenty-first century is significantly reliant on technological advancements, putting pressure on businesses' efficiency and performance and both employees and workers. Companies must develop methods to boost worker performance and productivity in such a setting (Agbenyiga, 2011).

The workplace setting and interactions between groups include the workforce, working conditions, and the relationship between employees and

management. Different work environments are established depending on the firm's responsibilities, model, culture, or history. Culture is regarded as the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group, and that it encompasses, in addition to art and literature; lifestyles, ways of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs (Douglas, 2004). It is however important to note that it is the "culture" to which various individuals belong in a society that makes the society multicultural (Alharbi & Alyahya, 2013). Every person by reason of being human has certain values that are upheld or abhorred. It is simply what makes us human. During the socialization process, the culture of a society is inculcated into the individual and this inherently forms part of human personalities. Cultural diversity evolved as direct impact of colonization, migration, trade globalization and has influenced the social work life and wellbeing (Parekh, 2005). The push to make social work services sensitive to those from various ethnic and cultural groups dates back nearly a century

Historical changes in culture in social services bring new challenges also in the context of support for employees. New values and philosophies have a decisive effect on changing culture that. An important factor of successful change is also the position and support of the employee in the new system of services, from which not only professional but also human and personal competencies are required. The current legislation reflects the support for social workers only in the area of professional development such as education, supervision, adaptation of the employee and as a way to ensure the quality of services. The legislation does not deal with other

dimensions of support for a social worker and their well-being.

The specificity of the profession is that it takes place basing on a close interpersonal relationship. The personality of social workers itself, its values, and human qualities are part of its working tools. However, this human capital, which social workers invest in their work, has its limits and needs to be renewed and supplemented, otherwise, there is a risk of emerging burnout syndrome. Research shows that workers in more demanding positions neglect self-care (Sahin, 2012). As this is a non-instinctive activity resulting from learning through interpersonal relationships, it is important, in order to protect social workers, to stimulate well-being activities through training, education, or support from the cultural influences.

Statement of the Problem

The challenges of the society today lead us to face different realities and occupy diverse professional spaces. Today's world is represented by a large interaction among people localized in all parts of the planet and by an intense movement of people, merchandise and services. In these activities, problems of a cultural nature emerge influencing, many times, the development of the negotiations. It is important that people who represent organizations become aware of the cultural differences and of the possible influences of these differences in the success of their jobs. It is predicated on the notion that psychological requirements underlie human behaviour. When one need is met, the person aspires to move up the hierarchy, where the need that follows becomes the most significant in determining behaviour. Cultural factors are one of the most frequent and difficult barriers to be overcome by anyone doing business. The problems facing in Nigeria is to adopt successful of diverse cultures and their impact on employee job performance. Those problems are power distance, individualism, uncertainty avoidance and masculinity. Such adaptation requires an understanding of culture, cultural diversity, views, stereotypes and values.

Apart from the above studies conflict on the influence of culture, the studies focused on the influence of corporate culture on employee performance and job satisfaction. Against this, this study wants to examine impact of cultural influence on social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. The following research questions were formulated:

- To what extent does cultural effectiveness impact on performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State?
- How does cultural involvement impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State?
- To what extent does cultural consistency relate to job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State?
- What is the impact of cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State?
- How does cultural flexibility impact on social development of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

Denison's theory

Denison's theory of organizational culture (2000) has been explored in this research as backed by Yilmaz (2008) that following Schien (1984) at the core of Denison's model are the underlying beliefs and assumptions that represent the deepest levels of organizational culture. These fundamental assumptions provide the foundation from which more surface-level cultural components such as values and observable artifacts symbols, heroes, rituals, among others are derived, and behavior and action spring (Denison, 2000). In Denison's model comparisons of organizations based on relatively more surface-level values and their manifest practices are made. Such values are deemed both more accessible than the assumptions and more reliable than the artifacts

(Denison, 2000 in Yilmaz, 2008). Denison’s organizational culture model is based on four cultural traits involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission that have been shown in the literature to have an influence on organizational performance (Denison, 1990; Denison & Mishra, 1995).

Social Exchange Theory

Social exchange theory, developed to explain the initiation, strengthening, and continued maintenance of interpersonal relationships, provides understanding relationships between individuals and their work organization (Blau, 2009). Individuals expect a response and an awarding in the context of this theory. These responses might be not only material or tangible facts, but also intangible facts such as friendship, interest, emotional support, social approval, respect, help and trust (Gouldner, 1960, Porath, 2010, Lambe et al., 2001 Blau, 2009). The parties of the social exchange should fulfill the rules arising from the mutual acceptance of those parties for the formation of trust, loyalty and commitment (Emerson, 1976). Thus, it is more possible for people (supervisor-employee) to become individuals who are glad to being together and serving the same purpose.

**Theory of Labor Welfare
Conceptual Framework**

This theory was developed by Aminul (2011). It is also called the efficiency theory. The theory states that a fully mentally and physically satisfied worker is the most efficient. Employee welfare is a means to keep organisation workers content so they may work effectively. In this theory, welfare work is used to secure, preserve and develop efficiency and productivity. This theory suggests that welfare work can be used to secure, maintain, and build efficiency and productivity (Manju & Mishra, 2007). The theory states that if an employer takes good care of his workforce, they will be more efficient by improving production. That program for housing, education, training, provision of balanced diet and family planning measures are essential for labour welfare as they increase the efficiency of workers in underdeveloped countries. The theory helps understand the characteristics of the labour force as reflected on the contemporary support for labour, and it works well if the employer and employees have the same goal of achieving higher production through better welfare. The theory is adopted in the study since welfare services affect the performance of any labour force. It was evident that if an employer takes good care of his workers, they will become more efficient.

Figure 1 conceptual framework on the impact of cultural influence on social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State.

Culture

Culture Different authors from different scientific fields are trying to define culture by starting off from different levels and forms. Culture is the shared values and beliefs that enable its members understand their roles and norms of the organization (Hodgetts, Luthans & Doh, 2006). Anthropologists see culture in many ways. For example, Kluckhohn (1951) Matijevic, Raguz & Filipovic (2012), one of the most widely used definition of culture is: Culture consists of explicit and implicit patterns, and behaviours acquired and transmitted symbols, which form the characteristic achievement group of people, including embodiments in artifacts; essential core of culture consists of traditional ideas and especially their values added; system of culture on the one hand can see as a product of action, on the other hand, as conditional elements of future action. Bahtijarevic-Siber and Sikavica (2001) noted that culture can be defined as a general pattern of behaviour, based on the values and beliefs that develop over time in a given society. These are common knowledge, beliefs, values, norms of behaviour and ways of opinions of members of a society.

Sources of Culture

Organizational culture may spring from different sources, mainly from the beliefs of the founders (Martínez-Cañas & Ruiz-Palomino, 2014; Schein, 2010). Uddin, Luva, and Hossian (2013) noted that the source of organizational culture also includes the learning experience of group members, as well as the new beliefs and assumptions of new members and managers. Founders have an opportunity to introduce a strategy and direction of the organization at an early stage of the organization. Founders have a significant

impact on how the organization operates (Andish, Yousefipour, Shahsavaripour, & Ghorbanipour, 2013). Founders of the organization are the primary source in establishing a new culture for the new organization (Flamholtz & Randle, 2012). The impact of culture occurs when the founders implement their business strategy and operational assumptions. Toma and Marinescu (2013) indicated that the founders' assumptions might develop because of their personal experience and cultural history.

History of Organizational Culture

In 1951, Jaques described an organizational culture in a business context that contained cultural issues in the manufacturing industry (as cited in Childress, 2013). In 1982, Peters and Waterman described the characteristics of higher performer companies' organizational culture. Peters and Waterman also profiled excellent companies in the United States based on their organizational culture. Recently many scholars published various books in the area of organizational culture that makes organizational culture a popular subject in the field of business and leadership.

Schein (1985) explained the importance of organizational culture in organizational performance by dividing organizational culture into three parts: assumptions, artifacts, and values. Assumptions reflect unofficial but important rules in the organization. Artifacts represent the visible elements of organizational culture including work process, the workplace setting, and organizational structures. The values represent the beliefs of the organization members and their business strategy (Childress, 2013). The three elements contribute to maintaining an effective culture in the organization.

Strong and Weak Organizational Culture

In a strong organizational culture, employees have similar views regarding the organization, and they behave consistently with organizational values (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). Business managers display a strong organizational culture to influence employees' work attitude and performance because

culture engages and motivates employees (Simoneaux & Stroud, 2014). In a strong organizational culture, the members of the organization share the values and goals of the organization, and new employees quickly adopt these values (Kotter & Heskett, 1992). Denison (1990) explained the impacts of organizational culture on business performance. A quantitative study results indicate a positive relationship between organizational culture and business performance (Han, 2012; Hartnell et al., 2011; Jofreh & Masoumi, 2013). A case study research results also show a strong culture as a driving factor for organizational performance (Pinho, Rodrigues, & Dibb, 2014; Simoneaux & Stroud, 2014).

Organizational Excellence

Maintaining a healthy working culture in the organization is important to promote a vision of excellence (Fusch & Gillespie, 2012). Bolboli and Reiche (2013) indicated that business excellence is a central feature for the success of any organization. Business excellence and organizational culture share common characteristics. Business excellence mainly includes effective organizational culture because effective organizational culture is a reflection of excellence in the organization (Brown, 2013).

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Positive Organizational Culture

Business managers may develop and maintain a positive organizational culture to improve organizational performance and productivity in the organization (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). Study findings in the area of organizational culture showed that a positive organizational culture as a functional culture in improving performance and productivity in the organization (Childress, 2013). Inabinett and Ballaro (2014) found the existence of a positive relationship between positive organizational culture and performance. Many business managers confirmed that a positive organizational culture as a primary factor in the success of their businesses (Childress, 2013; Melo, 2012). For example, the founders from Walmart and Southwest Airlines confirmed that their organizational culture is a primary factor in their business success (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). The founders of Google and Apple also identified their positive organizational culture as the ultimate source of sustainable competitive advantage (Simoneaux & Stroud, 2014).

Culture Effectiveness

The organizational culture literature contains information on how business managers use effective organizational culture to improve performance and productivity (Flamholtz & Randle, 2012; O'Reilly et al., 2014). Business managers believe that effective organizational culture is an asset, and ineffective culture is a liability for organizational success (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). Eaton and Kilby (2015) indicated that business managers use organizational

culture to control and moderate the working environment throughout the organization. Hartnell et al. (2011) noted that business managers use an effective organizational culture (a) to shape employee attitudes, (b) to improve operational effectiveness, and (c) to increase financial performance in the organization. Operational effectiveness contains information on how management uses an effective organizational culture to introduce and innovate new products and to improve process and service. Financial performance includes information regarding the achievement of profitability, productivity, and growth in the organization.

Types of Culture

Research findings in the area of organizational culture showed how clan culture positively relates to organizational performance (Han, 2012; Man & Luvison, 2014; Murphy et al., 2013). By contrast, Givens (2012) argued that clan culture includes employee relation issues instead of improving efficiency and effectiveness in the organization. Kotrba et al. (2012) compromised both views, supporting the clan culture's indirect role in improving performance and they acknowledge the clan culture's direct role in improving efficiency and effectiveness. In a clan culture, business managers encourage employee engagement and commitment to the organization because committed employees may perform their task efficiently and deliver their responsibility effectively (Nongo & Ikyanyon, 2012).

Social Workers

There is increasing recognition of the primary role of social work in promoting social development. This role is very critical in situations of persistent poverty since poverty has a crippling effect on the functioning and well-being of individuals in society. In view of this, social work has a critical role to play in Nigeria in contributing to efforts towards poverty eradication and the promotion of social development. Contextualisation of social work is important for

effective service delivery and sustainable social development. Clients shared their common problems as including income poverty, which affected their ability to have access to the basic services such as food, health, education and water. Similarly, child labour was reported particularly in rural and periurban areas. Other problems included poor infrastructure and unreliable transport to markets and other service centres.

Welfare Programmes

Welfare programmes amongst employed workers has generated significant interest by organizational practitioners, labour unions and employees themselves. Nigerian has witnessed series of strike actions by workers in most relevant sectors which include health and education, often targeted at improvement of the Welfare programmes of these workers. More so, the rate of turnover in organisation suggests that employees' Welfare programmes has not been satisfactory (Duijm, 2011). Hence, research interest into the possible factors that influences the Welfare programmes of workers cannot be overemphasized. The Welfare programmes of an employee is hinged on happiness, satisfaction and functioning well at work. The emphasis of employee Welfare programmes is beyond the absence of diseases rather a broader scope to encompass physical, emotional, mental and social aspect of work (Simone, 2014).

Empirical Review

Omoregbe, and Umemezia (2017) examined the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance in the Nigerian banking sector. The research made use of leadership styles, employee training, work process, and employee commitment as the dimensions of organizational culture. The study analyzed primary data from field survey using the questionnaire instrument. The sample size for the study consisted of 392 employees drawn through convenience and systematic sampling

techniques among employees of First Bank, Access Bank, Zenith Bank, Fidelity Bank, First City Monument Bank, United Bank for Africa, Diamond Bank and Guaranty Trust Bank, Nigeria. The model parameters used in the framework were estimated using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). Collected data were analyzed using SPSS 22.0 by running both descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings from the study revealed that there is a high level of organizational culture practices in the Nigerian banking sector. Organizational culture dimensions all had positive effects on employee's performance.

Ahmed (2020) on telecom industry in Pakistan revealed that there is a statistically significant association between organizational culture and employee productivity. The research used some Telecom franchisees in Bahawalpur and measured an organizations' productivity using the balanced scorecard. The findings showed that all aspects of organizational culture had a significant impact on several aspects of organizational productivity. Ng'ang'a and Wesonga (2020) discovered that organizational culture had a substantial impact on educational institution performance in Kenya. Return on equity, asset and profitability was used to evaluate the performance. The study discovered that culture is a crucial component of good organizational performance and that there is a strong link between culture and performance.

Mujeeb, Masood and Ahmad (2020) discovered a link between organizational culture and performance management techniques. The exploratory research approach was used to obtain data from 140 employees via primary means such as questionnaires. Inferential statistical procedures such as regression and correlation were utilized to analyze the data, which included both male and female faculty members. Involvement as a component of corporate culture was found to be substantially connected with consistency and adaptability. Tulcanaza-Prieto, Aguilar-

Rodríguez and Artieda (2021) researched of organizational culture and performance management procedures in information technology organizations were undertaken in Romania. The Chi-square test and bivariate analysis of primary data from 82 workers in the information technology business in Bucharest, Romania, revealed that organizational culture characteristics had a moderate effect on performance management. Also, involvement, consistency, adaptability and mission were significant and positive on performance management, Consistency also has the greatest influence on performance management approaches.

Narayana (2017) examined the effect of organizational culture on employee performance and its evaluation has been identified by certain researcher's research. The main aim of research article is to identify and determine strong relationship between organizational culture and employee performance. Literature review is adopted as methodology to review the culture of an organization upon employee performance. The owners and top management of an organization generally tends to have a large impact on establishing a culture. The Organization's culture results from the interaction between the top management's assumptions and shared visions of cultural values and human behavior and what the employees of the organization learn from their own experiences. Managers relate organizational culture and employee performance to each other as they help in providing competitive advantage to the organizations. Hence Organizational culture plays a vital role in enhancing employee performance. Organizational culture must be binding on all members and employees of the organization as this will encourage uniformity among members of the organization and this enhance commitment, group efficiency and overall performance of employees. Moruri (2018) conducted a study in Kenya that examined the relationship between motivational

factors and employees' performance in Kenya. The study employed a correlation survey design. The study population was 309, and through stratified sampling, the sample size was 179. Data were analysed by using inferential statistics of linear regression analysis. The findings had revealed that there is a positive and significant correlation between motivational factors and employees performance.

Literature Gap

The literature has been reviewed along the various variables of the study. Relevant concepts, competency theories and empirical studies were reviewed. Cultural influence and social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State was well reviewed. However, in the course of reviewing the literature, certain gaps were identified and the present study made efforts to close them. First, accessible studies to the best knowledge of the researcher made no efforts to identify challenges of cultural influence and the impact of cultural influence on social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. This study reported those methods and tools, thereby closing the literature gap. Again, a lot of researches studies have been carried out on assessment of examine impact of cultural influence on social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. This present study has provides the needed literature for future research studies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adopt for this study is descriptive survey of all the employees in in selected Local Government in Rivers State. According to Zikmund (2003) and Ahiauza (2001) a descriptive survey is concerned with the process of collecting data in order to test hypotheses and to answer questions concerning the current status of the phenomena under study.

Further, to the above, a descriptive research seeks to establish who, what, where, when and how much of the event. Adopting the survey design, the researcher described the variables of study and derives predictive regression models for predicting dependent variables.

Area of Study

The study covers selected Local Government Areas in Rivers State. On the 27th of May 1967, Rivers State was created together with eleven (11) others by the regime of the then Col. Yakubu Gowon (Ogan 2012, p. 47). It was a product of over two decades of political and constitutional struggles and the Nigerian political crisis of the 1960s.

Sampling Technique

The convenience sampling technique was used to reach out to the respondents. This is most suitable for the study because it gives the researcher the latitude to reach out to the respondents in a stress-free fashion.

Methods of Data Collection

The researcher and three trained research assistants will administer copies of questionnaire to local government staff collected in their various departments. The respondents will be given a period of two weeks to complete the questionnaire. After which the researcher and trained research assistant will go back to collect the questionnaire from various departments in the local government. The participants in the study will be senior staff (level 8 upward) selected from the six departments in the local governments.

Validity of Instruments

Validity refers to how well a test measures what it is purported to measure. That is the extent we are measuring what we hope to measure (and what we think we are measuring). The instrument for data collection will be validated by the researcher's supervisor, two lecturers in political science in order to scrutinize and make adjustments. The three experts will make necessary corrections and suggestions for

both face and content validity. Their ideas formed the basis for the modification of the instrument.

Reliability of Instruments

The reliability of instruments refers to the degree to which an assessment tool produces stable and consistent results. That is the extent to which an experiment test or any measuring procedure yields the same result on repeated trials. Therefore, the instrument for this study will be validated by the project supervisor. While the reliability of the questionnaire will be determined by a test - retest technique with a random sample of 50 respondents from two local governments not included in the study. A one month interval will be given between the first and second tests to ensure its reliability overtime.

Methods of Data Collection

The data needed for this study was obtained from primary source. The primary sources covered mainly the administration of questionnaires. The primary data collection methods used for this study were retrieving the questionnaire group scores for each respondent. The data for this study was collected through the use of questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured in a simple and direct method, and also, complex questions were avoided. The variables of the study, both predictors and criterion variables, are measured using the 4-point Likert scale (where, 4 = strongly agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = strongly disagree, 1 = disagree. the instrument is titled: **Impact of Cultural Influence on Social Workers in Community Development and Welfare Programs in Selected Local Governments in Rivers State.**

The research questionnaire fielded multiple choice questions and closed questions about the study. The questionnaire was based on a 4-point Likert scale. It consists of closed questions and is divided into two sections A and B. Section A consist of issues that measure the personal profile and demographic characteristics of the respondents. Section B consists of issues that measure the research questions.

Methods of Data Analysis

The copies of the questionnaires administered were retrieved upon completion from the respondents. Furthermore, the collected data was analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative data analysis approaches with the help of a computer software; Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. Quantitative approach will be descriptive, where simple frequencies and percentages were used. Data will be presented in tables and figures. The data gather the following areas: respondents' academic qualification, years of service, gender, experience. Qualitative data analysis will be conducted on the data which were collected using questionnaire method from the parents and teachers. Data collected were coded in to themes. This involves grouping the responses according to their respective themes. The themes will be basically fall under respective research areas which was informed by research objectives.

The statistical techniques employed in analyzing data collected in this study are:

• Tables

Tables effectively order and summarize the quantitative data. They are used to arrange facts and figures in columns and rows. These facts and figures can be systematically examined. (Ojo, 2005)

• Percentages

These are used in translating frequency counts into percentage. These percentages were used to show the distribution of respondents according to their responses (Ojo, 2005)

• Correlation Analysis

It is used as a measure of the strength of linear dependence between two variables. According to Ojo (2005) correlation is used to find out if there is any relationship between two variables. While doing this, a variable is correlation to another variable. Spearman rank correlation coefficient with the aid of the

Statistical Package for Social Sciences, (SPSS) Version 20.0. It is mathematically stated below

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6\sum d^2}{n^3 - n}$$

Where:

$\sum d^2$ = sum of the squared differences in the ranking of the subject on two variables.

n = Number of subject being ranked

d = the difference between each subjects rank

The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1. A value of 1 implies that a linear equation describes the relationship between X and Y perfectly, with all factors affecting Y held constant for which Y increases as X increases. A value of -1 implies Y decreases as X increases. A value of 0 implies that there is no linear correlation between the variables.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Age

	Age	Response	Percentage
a)	20-29years	170	44.7
b)	30-39years	180	47.3
c)	40years and above	50	8
	Total	400	100

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 2 above shows that most of the respondents were between the age of 30 and 39 years. The implication of this result is that the actual target audience that participated in the study was those who were still within child bearing age.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Educational qualification

	Educational qualification	Response	Percentage
3) a	FSLC	63	16.6
b	ND/HND	78	20.5
c	BA/B.SC	126	33.2
d	MA/M.SC	57	15
e	PhD	27	1.9
f	None	49	12.8
	Total	400	100

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

The decision rule is stated as follows:

P-value < 0.05; Reject null hypothesis and accept alternate

P-value > 0.05; Reject alternate and accept null hypothesis

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study adopted a survey research design. To this end, a total of 400 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents and all 400 copies of the questionnaire were properly filled out and retrieved. This represents a 100% retrieval rate. The availability random sampling technique was used to select respondents for the survey.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Sex

S/N	Sex	Response	Percentage
a)	Female	226	59.5
b)	Male	174	39.5
	Total	400	100

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 1 indicates that there were more females than males among the respondents that participated in the study.

Table 3 Data shows that the majority of the respondent had Bachelor Degrees or Bachelor of Science as their highest educational qualification. The implication of this result is that more educated individuals participated in the survey, which lends some credence to the quality of their responses on the objectives being canvassed. However, those without any form of education were 49 (12.8%). These ones were guided on how to fill the questionnaire.

Table 4: Research question one: Cultural effectiveness and performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State

S/N	Questionnaire items	Responses				N	$\sum \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
1.	Effective is needed in social worker performance	180	160	40	20	400	1300	3.25	Accepted
2.	We need effective culture to achieve the aim of social worker performance	80	70	12	130	400	900	2.25	Rejected
3.	Cultural effectiveness relate to social worker performance	120	145	55	80	400	1105	2.76	Accepted
4.	Cultural effectiveness determine social worker performance	90	70	12	120	400	930	2.32	Rejected
5.	Effectiveness of culture is desired in the process of social worker performance	150	160	50	40	400	1220	3.05	Accepted

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 4 examined the cultural effectiveness and performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. From the table, out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent’s opinion on the cultural effectiveness and performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed.

Table 5: Research question two: Cultural involvement and the impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State

S/no	Questionnaire items	Responses				N	$\sum \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
6.	Workers needs to be part of the culture for the growth of social workers	180	165	35	20	400	1325	3.31	Accepted
7.	We need to integrate the culture to social workers for the growth of social workers	200	180	20	-	400	1380	3.45	Accepted
8.	There is need for cultural involvement for the growth of social workers	165	170	50	15	400	1285	3.21	Accepted
9.	The importance of cultural involvement is to enhance growth of social workers	200	180	15	5	400	1375	3.44	Accepted
10.	There is need for cultural involvement for the growth of social workers	90	70	120	120	400	930	2.32	Rejected

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 5 presents respondents opinion on Cultural involvement and the impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. From the table,

out of the five items, the results accepted four out of the five items while one was rejected, this implies that the respondent's opinion on Cultural involvement and the impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed.

Table 6 Research question three: cultural consistency and job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State

S/no	Questionnaire items	Responses				N	$\sum \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
11.	Culture need to be consistent with social workers	120	145	55	80	400	1105	2.76	Accepted
12.	Inconsistent culture challenges the objectives of the social workers	200	180	15	5	400	1375	3.44	Accepted
13.	Consistent culture enhances the performance of the social workers	80	70	120	130	400	900	2.25	Rejected
14.	The importance of cultural consistency is to enhance job satisfaction of social workers	165	170	50	15	400	1285	3.21	Accepted
15.	There is need for cultural consistency for the satisfaction of social workers	85	70	110	135	400	905	2.26	Rejected

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 6 presents respondents opinion on cultural consistency and job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. From the table, out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent's opinion on Cultural consistency and job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed.

Table 7: The impact of cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State

S/N	Questionnaire items	Responses				N	$\sum \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
16.	Culture need to be adaptable by social workers	165	170	50	15	400	1285	3.21	Accepted
17.	Unadaptable challenges the objectives of the social workers	70	85	110	135	400	890	2.22	Rejected
18.	Adaptable culture enhances the performance of the social workers	200	180	20	-	400	1380	3.45	Accepted
19.	The importance of cultural adaptability is to enhance success of social workers	165	170	50	15	400	1285	3.21	Accepted
20.	There is need for cultural adaptability for the success of social workers	80	70	120	130	400	900	2.25	Rejected

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 7 focused on the impact of cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. From the table, out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent’s opinion on the cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed.

Table 8: Research question five, cultural flexibility impact on social development of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State

S/N	Questionnaire items	Responses				N	$\sum \bar{X}$	Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD				
1.	Culture need to be flexible	170	150	55	25	400	1250	3.15	Accepted
2.	Social workers can achieve its aim from flexible culture	60	65	12	15	400	800	2.05	Rejected
3.	Flexible culture enhances the performance of the social workers	130	145	55	60	400	1115	2.96	Accepted
4.	The importance of cultural flexibility is to enhance success of social workers	80	60	13	13	400	946	2.32	Rejected
5.	There is need for cultural flexibility for the success of social workers	160	150	50	40	400	1242	3.15	Accepted

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 8 focused on the impact of cultural flexibility impact on social development of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. From the table, out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent’s opinion on the cultural flexibility on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed.

Discussion of Findings

Research question was formulated to examine the impact of effectiveness on performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. From table 4, out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent’s opinion on

the cultural effectiveness and performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed. The findings of the study confirm the findings of Omoregbe, and Umemezia (2017) that there is a high level of organizational culture practices in the Nigerian banking sector. Organizational culture dimensions all had positive effects on employee’s performance, the findings of Ahmed (2020) that all aspects of organizational culture had a significant impact on several aspects of organizational productivity, the findings of Ng’ang’a and Wesonga (2020) that organizational culture had a substantial impact on educational institution performance in Kenya, the findings of Mujeeb, Masood and Ahmad (2020) that Involvement as a component of corporate culture was found to be substantially connected with consistency and adaptability and the findings of

Tulcanaza-Prieto, Aguilar-Rodríguez and Artieda (2021) that organizational culture characteristics had a moderate effect on performance management and that involvement, consistency, adaptability and mission were significant and positive on performance management, Consistency also has the greatest influence on performance management approaches. Research question two was formulated to examine how cultural involvement impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. from the results presented in table 5, out of the five items, the results accepted four out of the five items while one was rejected, this implies that the respondent's opinion on cultural involvement and the impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed. The findings of research question two is in line with the findings of Nazir, Zamir S (2015) that employee performance and organizational culture were found to have a favorable and strong significant association, according to the t-tests and Pearson correlation matrices. The study also discovered that there was no statistically significant difference in employee responses to organizational culture and performance based on gender, the findings of Adam Jiddah and Umar M (2016) that consistency was a significant determinant of an employees' effectiveness, and the mission of an institution also had a significant effect on job efficiency. The research also discovered a link between company culture and employee productivity, Shahzad, Iqbal and Gulzar (2013) that culture of organizations has the significant positive impact on employee's job performance at selected software houses in Pakistan. Employees' participation is a most important factor for achieving organizational goals and the findings of Njugi and Nickson (2014) that organization culture has a great influence on performance as it dictates how things are done,

organization's philosophy, work environment, performance targets and organizations stability.

The purpose of research question three was to examine cultural consistency and the impact on job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent's opinion on Cultural consistency and job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed. This is in line with the findings of Oduol (2015) that firms engaged in various organizational cultures so as to boost performance and that the provision of rules that provided clear instructions, processes and procedures for employees was the most prevalent culture, the findings of Wambugu (2014) that managers should focus on the factors that have a significant effect on employee performance, if they want to enhance their businesses. Based on the results, this study was able to revealed that organizational values have a more significant effect to employee's job performance at Wärtsilä, than the organization climate as is mostly assumed as a vice versa relationship. Overly a positive relationship between organization culture and employee performance was established, however the effect diversely varied amongst the variables with work processes and systems in Wärtsilä having more effect to employee's performance.

The fourth research questions was formulated to examine the impact of cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State. the study found that, out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent's opinion on the cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development

and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed. The findings of the study is in line with the findings of Narayana (2017) that organization's culture results from the interaction between the top management's assumptions and shared visions of cultural values and human behavior and what the employees of the organization learn from their own experiences. Managers relate organizational culture and employee performance to each other as they help in providing competitive advantage to the organizations, Dimitrios and Athanasios (2014) that contemporary job-related phenomena like job satisfaction are related to their perceptions of their working environment, relations with colleagues, institution aims and strategies and success criteria, the findings of Gunaraja (2014) that there is no positive relationship between corporate sectors organizational culture and organizational productivity in Indian banking industry through survey method and that a large number of respondents almost more than half of the respondent strongly agree that organizational corporate culture has influence on employee work performance, and that nearly half of the employees also agree that culture of corporate sector determines the level of productivity of the organization.

The fifth research question was formulated to examine the how cultural flexibility impact on social development of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State, findings of the study revealed that out of the five items, the results accepted three out of the five items while two were rejected, this implies that the respondent's opinion on the cultural flexibility on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed. The finding is supported by the empirical findings of Massudi (2013) that the factors that motivate employees to perform effectively are salary

increment, promotion, and recognition. Manyenga (2016) that the motivational factors of job security, recognition, promotion, and attractive working environment play a significant role in boosting the work performance of employees at the organisations, Moruri (2018) that there is a positive and significant correlation between motivational factors and employees performance. It recommended that workers should be provided with working facilities such as health benefits and housing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study examined cultural influence of social workers and community development, welfare programs in selected local government areas in Rivers State. From the findings, the study conclude that opinion on the cultural effectiveness and performance of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed, that the respondent's opinion on cultural involvement and the impact on growth of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed, that the respondent's opinion on Cultural consistency and job satisfaction of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed, that the respondent's opinion on the cultural adaptability on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed and that the respondent's opinion on the cultural flexibility on success of social workers in community development and welfare programs in selected Local Governments in Rivers State were mixed.

Recommendations

❖ Thus, the study recommended that social workers in the selected Local Governments in Rivers State should adopt culture that best enhances

employee performance and efforts should be directed to ensure effectiveness of culture in the local governments.

❖ The study recommended that local government councils should ensure that incentives are provided to staff and ensure that the culture of the area is integrated with the objectives and the operational order of the social workers

❖ Workers should be provided with all trainings and orientations to ensure that culture is consistent with social workers in the local government as this can enhance the performance and welfare of the people.

❖ Culture is an essential ingredient of social worker performance and welfare, the study recommends that the local government should and the social workers should ensure that cultures are adaptable.

❖ Culture is an important element to unify various social workers, the study recommend that culture should be made flexible for the social workers to achieve development and welfare of the people.

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